

Template synthesis of Mn^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles derived from 2,3-butanedione and diaminoalkanes

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Mn^{II} complexes of the type [MnL(NO₃)₂] (where L = macrocycle having 16 to 32-membered ring incorporating N₄ donor set) have been synthesized by the reactions of 2,3-butanedione with diaminoalkanes such as 1,4-diaminobutane, 1,5-diaminopentane, 1,6-diaminohexane, 1,7-diaminoheptane, 1,8-diaminooctane, 1,9-diaminononane, 1,10-diaminodecane and 1,12-diaminododecane in the presence of Mn²⁺ as a template. These have been characterized by elemental analyses, conductances, magnetic moments and diffuse reflectance and IR spectra.

Tetraazamacrocyclic complexes of transition metals have been widely studied due to their biological relevance. Several macrocyclic complexes of manganese have been studied as models for superoxide dismutase activity¹. TIM and PhTIM complexes of transition metals have been synthesized by the reactions of the α-diketones with 1,3-diaminopropane in the presence of metal ions as templates². Mn^{II,3} and Mn^{III,4} complexes of several other tetraazamacrocycles have been reported. However, Mn^{II} complexes of large ring tetraazamacrocycles derived from α-diketones and higher aliphatic diamines have not been studied so far. Earlier, Cr^{III} and Fe^{III} complexes of such tetraazamacrocycles have been reported from these laboratories⁵. In the present paper Mn^{II} complexes of the tetraazamacrocycles derived from 2,3-butanedione and various diaminoalkanes such as 1,4-diaminobutane, 1,5-diaminopentane, 1,6-diaminohexane, 1,7-diaminoheptane, 1,8-diaminooctane, 1,9-diaminononane, 1,10-diaminodecane and 1,12-diaminododecane are described.

Results and discussion

The reactions of Mn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O with 2,3-butanedione and different aliphatic diamines such as 1,4-diaminobutane, 1,5-diaminopentane, 1,6-diaminohexane, 1,7-diaminoheptane, 1,8-diaminooctane, 1,9-diaminononane, 1,10-diaminodecane or 1,12-diaminododecane in 1 : 2 : 2 molar ratios, result in the formation of macrocyclic complexes (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Synthesis of macrocyclic complexes.

The resulting macrocyclic complexes are brown solids insoluble in water, methanol, acetone, carbon tetrachloride, acetonitrile, nitromethane and chloroform and soluble in dimethyl sulphoxide. The characteristics and analyses of the complexes are given in Table 1.

In the IR spectra of macrocyclic complexes of Mn^{II} a strong absorption band at 1600–1640 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to νC=N^{3,6}. Strong absorption bands at 720, 830 and 1380 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ionic nitrate and bands at 1000–1030 cm⁻¹ and 1500–1530 cm⁻¹ are due to unidentate nitrate^{6,7}. Thus the appearance of bands due to both coordinated as well as ionic nitrate suggests that nitrate groups are

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of Mn^{II} tetraazamacrocyclic complexes

Compd.	Colour and decomp. temp.	Yield (%)	Analyses (%):		Conductance ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Found (Calcd.)			
			N	Mn		
[Mn(Me ₄ 16]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 130	70	12.45 (12.30)	12.21 (12.06)	91	5.34
[Mn(Me ₄ 18]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 135	73	11.71 (11.58)	11.58 (11.36)	87	5.14
[Mn(Me ₄ 20]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 125	74	11.08 (10.95)	10.98 (10.74)	56	4.82
[Mn(Me ₄ 22]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 132	62	10.50 (10.38)	10.21 (10.18)	60	5.66
[Mn(Me ₄ 24]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 140	68	9.96 (9.87)	9.72 (9.67)	59	5.14
[Mn(Me ₄ 26]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 138	31	9.53 (9.40)	9.40 (9.22)	67	5.31
[Mn(Me ₄ 28]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 150	26	9.13 (8.98)	8.98 (8.80)	70	5.25
[Mn(Me ₄ 32]tetraeneN ₄)(NO ₃) ₂]	Brown 155	34	8.48 (8.24)	8.19 (8.08)	78	5.35

weakly coordinated to the metal atom giving distorted octahedral geometry.

Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of the complexes in DMSO fall in the range $56\text{--}91 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ indicating them to be 2 : 1 electrolytes⁸. Thus it appears that the nitrate groups, which are weakly coordinated, as evidenced by IR spectra, are replaced by the solvent molecules.

The μ_{eff} values of Mn^{II} tetraazamacrocyclic complexes correspond to high spin $d^5 \text{Mn}^{2+}$ state (Table 1). The lower values of magnetic moments may be due to the presence of traces of Mn^{III} formed as a result of aerial oxidation of Mn^{II} during synthesis⁹.

The diffuse reflectance spectra of Mn^{II} tetraazamacrocyclic complexes exhibit bands in the region $13698\text{--}14285 \text{cm}^{-1}$ which may be charge transfer bands. Bands in the region $18000\text{--}18200$ and $24213\text{--}25000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ may be assigned to ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(S)$ and ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4E_g + {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ multiplicity forbidden transitions respectively¹⁰. Thus the electronic spectral findings favour the geometry to be octahedral for Mn^{II} complexes.

Experimental

1,4-Diaminobutane (Aldrich), 1,5-diaminopentane (Aldrich), 1,6-diaminohexane (Merck), 1,7-diaminoheptane (Aldrich) and 2,3-butanedione (Aldrich) were distilled before use. 1,8-Diaminooctane (Merck), 1,9-diaminononane (Fluka), 1,10-diaminododecane (Fluka) and 1,12-diaminododecane (Aldrich) were used as supplied. Mn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (Fluka) was of A.R. grade.

Manganese was estimated volumetrically using EDTA¹¹. Nitrogen was determined by Kjeldahl's method. Molar conductances of $10^{-3} M$ solutions of the complexes were measured in DMSO using Systronics direct reading conductivity meter-304; cell constant 1.0cm^{-1} . Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded as KBr pellets in the region $400\text{--}4000 \text{cm}^{-1}$ on Nicolet Magna-550 FT IR spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were carried out in solid state at room temperature on Gouy balance using Hg[Co(SCN)₄] as calibrant at Banasthali Vidyapith, Banasthali, Rajasthan. Diffuse reflectance spectra of the solid compounds suitably diluted with MgO were measured on a Beckman-DU spectrophotometer with standard Beckman reflectance attachment at S. P. University, Vallabh Vidyanagar (Gujarat).

Synthesis of Mn^{II} complexes of tetraazamacrocycles derived from 2,3-butanedione and diaminoalkanes: Mn(NO₃)₂·4H₂O (1.0 mmol) was dissolved in 25 ml *n*-butanol and 2,3-butanedione (2.0 mmol in ~ 20 ml *n*-butanol) was added with stirring. To this, a solution of 2.0 mmol of aliphatic diamine (1,4-diaminobutane, 1,5-diaminopentane, 1,6-diaminohexane, 1,7-diaminoheptane, 1,8-diaminooctane, 1,9-diaminononane, 1,10-diaminododecane or 1,12-diaminododecane) in ~ 25 ml *n*-butanol was added dropwise with constant stirring. The stirring was continued for ~ 5 h. The solid product was filtered, washed with *n*-butanol and dried under reduced pressure.

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